

UK Research
and Innovation

Driving Research Excellence through institutional support for technical and specialist capability

**A UKRI event in partnership with
the UK Institute for Technical Skills & Strategy**

Introduction

UKRI, in partnership with the UK Institute for Technical Skills & Strategy, hosted an event on 12 June 2025 to explore how institutional support and investment in technical and specialist capability could drive research excellence.

The event explored how structural interventions to build capability and implement new ways of working had supported high-performing, efficient and inclusive research environments that improved the quality and reliability of research outputs.

The event was attended by a mix of institutional research leaders; strategic technical leaders; members of the REF29 People, Culture and Environment pilot panels; and representatives of research funders and national funding bodies.

Speakers presented a series of institutional case studies and attendees discussed the potential impact of these approaches. Furthermore, attendees discussed the culture shifts that may be required to ensure benefits from each intervention would be captured. The event highlighted the contribution of a range of roles to research excellence, ensuring Research Organisations (ROs) with a demonstrable strategic approach to their people and teams were a compelling and safe environment for UKRI investment.

Interventions

Event attendees heard and discussed examples from organisations who had invested in interventions in developing their technical and specialist capabilities. Our case studies fell into two groups:

The development of a specific technical and specialist function, in this case digital. This was demonstrated by UCL's Advanced Research Computing Centre (ARC) and The Research Software and Analytics Group at the University of Exeter.

The second group of case studies looked at the consolidation of technical infrastructure and research facilities into a single strategic function, as in the case of Research and Infrastructure Facilities at the University of Bath and Research Technology Platforms at the University of Warwick.

A common mechanism across these interventions was the move of expertise and effort from within research groups into cross-cutting functions, leading to institution-wide benefits. Though these approaches demonstrate a range of benefits to the efficiency and effectiveness of research and to the people and teams carrying out the research, some structural and cultural barriers to implementation were raised and discussed.

Further details on the individual case studies are presented at the end of this summary report.

Benefits

Both types of intervention presented a range of benefits to the research performance of the organisation and to the people and teams carrying out the research themselves. These included:

Improved cost recovery of technical and specialist resources and facilities through centralised oversight, management and support with costing grant applications, including a trend towards increased grant application success rates.

Reduced staff turnover and reduced precarity, along with greater attraction and retention of technical and specialist roles within the team.

Higher quality of service delivery as staff had the necessary depth of technical expertise to support R&I projects and could keep their knowledge up to date with cutting-edge developments.

Agility and depth of expertise, allowing projects to be supported on an 'as needed' basis, recognising skills needs may change over the lifetime of a project; providing the same support better and less costly than hiring equivalent staff over the lifetime of a project.

And reduced administrative burden through centralised systems, records and providing expertise in, for example, data management.

Some benefits extended beyond the functions themselves, such as:

Providing the RO with a pool of experts that could provide doctoral training and upskill the rest of the organisation in emerging technologies such as AI and/or improve institutions' resilience to cybersecurity threats.

Embedded cross-disciplinary ways of working that helped bridge knowledge silos and seed ideas across the organisation.

And improved sustainability and resilience of capability and capacity at the institution.

Together, these add up to significant economic and performance benefits for the organisation, ensuring value for money, improving efficiency, and reducing burden on staff.

Challenges

Presenters highlighted challenges that they had needed to overcome to achieve their successes. As with any change initiative, there were processes to change, people to influence and pressures to succeed. The challenges included:

Securing investment required a strong business case as these initiatives often carried significant up-front cost and therefore financial risk. Securing investment requires pulling together data from a range of sources, sometimes exposing uncomfortable gaps in current cost recovery against the true cost of the facility or equipment in question.

There was further pressure to demonstrate cost recovery and meet the expectations of senior leaders once the intervention was in place, which required careful thought and embedding the appropriate processes and KPIs from the beginning to ensure the right evidence was available. Cost recovery often required a critical mass of technical and specialist capability to be reached.

Establishing new ways of working was essential but pushed against long established, often locally held processes. The cultural shift could prove challenging and change slow. There was also fear of loss of control from academic colleagues as equipment and facilities were centralised, though this often dissipated in those working most closely with the function once the benefits were apparent.

Strategic use of institutional research funding

Contributors emphasised the importance of the variety of flexible funding mechanisms such as Research England [Strategic Institutional Research Funding \(SIRF\)](#) streams, and devolved nation equivalents. These flexible funding mechanisms enable investment in building capability and underpinning the transition into more effective and efficient staffing models. Thus moving to a cost-recovery footing.

This type of strategic approach was enabled by cross subsidy from other income streams. Although once up and running the interventions were cost neutral or cheaper, the start-up investment often required the use of flexible and underpinning funding provided by, in these cases, Research England.

Research user journeys

From a research user perspective, technical and specialist functions can contribute at each stage of the research journey:

Idea

Idea

The cross cutting nature of these roles can transfer knowledge across disciplinary silos, enabling collaborations and seeding ideas for new projects.

Costing and bidding

Costing and bidding

Support in costing research grants, developing bids and meeting funder requirements on, for example, data management plans.

Starting the work

Starting the work

Technical and specialist expertise resourced to grants can start as needed. This reduces delays to project starts through, for example, avoiding recruitment delays or mandatory training for new hires to be certified in certain techniques or equipment.

Delivery

Delivery

Skills and expertise needs may change over the lifetime of the project. A software engineering and/or research computing function, for example, has the depth of expertise to meet changing needs over the lifetime of the project, avoiding the need for extra training or hiring additional staff.

Publication

Publication

Technical and specialist roles can support publication and knowledge transfer through data analysis and visualisation, drafting and supporting researchers to meeting open research requirements, curating data and reproducible coding.

Close of project

Close of project

Project data can be curated, labelled and archived efficiently, meeting funding requirements. Project leads can benefit from efficient workflows in reporting and disseminating research outcomes.

Attendee insights

Event attendees contributed their insights through round table discussion, with outputs gathered using the Mentimeter platform. Discussion topics and key themes are summarised below.

Prompt: How can shared infrastructure and digital capabilities enable an inclusive and high-performing research culture?

Bringing together shared physical and digital infrastructures supported openness in research design and dissemination of outputs, through making it easy for researchers to meet Open Research requirements and embed open ways of working. There were similar benefits from greater digital integration in enabling reproducibility and enhancing the reliability of research outputs. Integration of physical and digital infrastructures was felt to be the most effective use of scarce resources.

Consolidation and strategic oversight of infrastructure facilities enabled economies of scale. Equipment downtime was reduced enabling more efficient planning and sustainability. Capability was easier to maintain through enhanced cost recovery and enabled high-level expertise on demand with less time spent reinventing the wheel.

Team Science (Team Research) was easier, with specialists acting to bridge disciplinary siloes, work across research groups and cross-pollinate ideas, enhancing opportunities in curiosity-driven research, improving research creativity and enabling knowledge exchange. Specialists could support the development of other staff, upskill users, and reducing boundaries between 'in' and 'out' groups.

Sustainable staffing models reduced staff turnover, enabled inclusive working practices that enabled a greater diversity of people to participate in R&I.

Better integration of both physical and digital facilities enabled consolidation of access, costing and booking systems, reducing transactional friction and pain points for users, perceived as a reduction in institutional bureaucracy.

Prompt: What is good research, technical and specialist leadership in an environment of increasingly complex, challenging and interdisciplinary research?

Focusing on what capabilities distinguished good leaders in these environments, the attendees raised the following:

For research leaders, a clear vision for their research programme and the ability to clearly communicate it, motivating a diverse range of team members without formal authority over them.

Openness to new ways of working, with the willingness and ability to challenge the status quo. Driving culture change and valuing the expertise of a wide range of contributors.

Being able to respond with agility, seizing new opportunities and being adaptable to changing circumstances.

Prompt: How do we encourage the sector to consider the impact of structures and capabilities on research performance and improving research outcomes?

There was general recognition that we arrived at our current ways of working through a range of financial incentives on both research organisations and individuals within them. Although well intended, they combined in some problematic ways. Changing to more efficient and effective ways of working would require changing the financial incentives behind research funding. This could be via REF, specifically the new People, Culture and Environment Indicators; or through recognising the value of technical and specialist capabilities in how research funding applications were assessed and awarded. The latter would benefit from greater inclusion of technical and specialist expertise at both bid development stages within the proposing organisation, and in assessment of funding applications within research funders.

Embedding such incentives would be strengthened through providing evidenced case studies of the value of specialist and technical expertise and sustained effort in championing such change to build momentum and disseminate these messages widely across the sector.

The importance of sharing practice

Event attendees recognised the importance of sharing practice across the community, which was also a key objective of the event. Attendees noted the efforts some of our institutions had made to disseminating their work and supporting other research organisations to support their own specialist functions.

Many functions were able to provide services to other Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), enabling 'equipment sharing' with their specialist and technical capability through costing the function on the partner institution's grant applications. Such practice exchange was positive in building connections between ROs and provided evidence on the value of specialist and technical capability to the partner RO.

UCL ARC specifically was noted as the template for software engineering functions in other institutions, based on a deliberate effort to share practice and provide resources that others could use. These resources included job descriptions for each of their professional pathways, along with positive engagement and staff with dedicated partnership and engagement responsibilities.

Should we talk about strategy and environment differently?

A key takeaway from the event was that research environments were far more than how the people and teams designing and delivering research treated each other. Collegiate and collaborative environments were necessary, but without senior intervention and strategic ownership of institutions' people and environment – that made it easier for those people and teams to perform at their best – this was not sufficient. This was exemplified in the discussion around [Hidden REF](#), an initiative that captures the contributions of the full range of R&I roles, recognising the difference team members from a diversity of professions can make beyond publications.

The fundamental observation and recommendation emerging from this event is that good research environments are those that enabled high performance in research through thinking boldly about how each member of a research team could contribute fully and building the systems and structures that enabled research investments to make the biggest difference.

The approach taken to optimise ways of working demonstrates strategic consideration of an institution's working environment and culture, ensuring the whole functions as much more than the sum of its parts and presenting a safe and compelling environment for investment in R&I.

About ITSS

The UK Institute for Technical Skills and Strategy (UK ITSS), funded by Research England and UKRI, operates across the higher education, research and innovation sectors to strengthen and sustain the UK's technical workforce. It leads a national portfolio of activity focused on developing technical skills, enabling career progression and supporting early entry into technical professions through initiatives such as T Levels and apprenticeships. At the heart of UK ITSS is the Technician Commitment – a national initiative now embedded within the Institute that drives visibility, recognition, career development and sustainability for technical professionals across more than 140 organisations. Building on the legacy and impact of the TALENT Programme and Commission, UK ITSS provides strategic leadership and coordination for this growing community. The Institute champions the essential role of technical professionals who enable excellence in both education and research.

Case study

Digital and software engineering teams

UCL: Advanced Research Computing Centre (ARC)

University of Exeter: Research Software and Analytics Group

UCL and the University of Exeter both operate highly developed Data, Research Software Engineering, and Analytics functions, differing in size based on the resources of their host institution and their level of maturity.

ARC has open sourced its career structures and job descriptions. Alongside proactive engagement with ROs across the sector, this enables institutions like Exeter to build their own Research Software and Analytics group, taking advantage of prior work and lessons learned, and strengthening the internal business case for investment in a digital function. The ARC now offers a hub and spoke model, enabling staff to carve out disciplinary expertise and enhancing the value of the support they offer.

What problems does this try to solve?

Digital and software engineering skills are highly in demand as they become more sought after both within R&I and the economy more broadly. Recruitment of digital professionals has become increasingly difficult into the fixed term, project-based model of employment in academic research organisations when competing against the pay, job security and career value proposition offered by employers outside of an academic environment. This difficulty is evident when considering factors like opportunities for career advancement, which are notably absent outside of the linear PhD to Professor academic career pathway in most HEIs.

It has often been left to individual research teams and individual team members to develop workarounds and build just enough understanding to deliver the projects, which embeds inefficiencies and leads to inconsistent standards of research.

How does it work?

The institutions developed a flexible pool of experts that can be costed to research projects on an as-needed basis. The on-demand nature of skills provision ensures that, should project needs change over the lifetime of the project, they can be met, whilst ensuring retention of expertise within the organisation. The opportunity cost of having a staff member dedicated to the project is reduced where their skills may not be needed for the entirety of the project.

In both models, team members are employed on permanent contracts, enabling long-term planning based on expected grant income for the organisation and providing the critical mass of resource to enable career pathways for specialists.

Whilst ARC generates a surplus that is reinvested into the function, Exeter has made a deliberate choice to limit cost recovery to around 80-85% from research income, keeping 15-20% of staff time back for building and maintaining the capability of the function.

What are the benefits to researchers and Research Organisations?

The key benefits of both ARC and Exeter models include:

More efficient delivery of research projects through being able to provide the relevant expertise on demand, reducing downtime in available resources and lengthy delays due to recruitment and staff turnover.

An increase in expertise available which improves the quality of research outputs, and their reproducibility. Reported improvement in grant success rates.

A decrease in administration burden around access to skills, in delivering data-intensive research due to more optimised, accessible workflows and systems.

A varied and diverse workload for team members which enables them to build a portfolio of skills across the organisation, strengthening the professional community, reducing isolation, and seeding ideas and practice across disciplinary boundaries, making these functions a key means of connectivity and knowledge exchange across silos, enhancing the creativity of research ideas.

Both functions provide wider support to their organisation, enabling them to capitalise on new opportunities around, for example, AI, and to use this expertise in training and developing both their staff and students.

Case study

Consolidated infrastructure and facilities

University of Bath: Research Infrastructure and Facilities

University of Warwick: Research Technology Platforms

The universities of Bath and Warwick have brought their infrastructure, facilities and technical service provision under a centralised model, enabling central oversight and understanding of the organisation's portfolio of both capital and people, and harmonisation of systems, service provision and 'back office' support for the portfolio. Applying a similar model to their unique circumstances.

What problems does this try to solve?

Provision of infrastructure, facilities and technical services was inconsistent across both types of facility and the time users accessed the facility. The inconsistency was driven by funding cycles, lack of underpinning financial support, and the consequent impact on skills available to provide the relevant expertise. Loss of institutional memory from staff turnover, lack of dedicated staff development, and siloed approaches to staffing led to researchers struggling to access systems.

Increased equipment downtime reduced utilisation rates and caused equipment duplication.

The lack of provision of essential equipment and facilities was underpinned by the absence of strategic consideration of both the portfolios.

Furthermore, isolated equipment was prone to gatekeeping by individual project leads in order to protect their investment. Varying systems, access, training and booking systems resulted in increased administrative burdens on users and increased challenges in the research data produced.

How does it work?

Central oversight of an RO's portfolio allows it to understand and address issues in how equipment is costed, where there may be potential duplication, where space is best utilised, and to enable more strategic planning of what to buy, what supplier relationships to build and how equipment can be best utilised.

Bringing facilities together allows for a critical mass in technical talent, with effective cross training across different pieces of equipment, amortised by spreading the cost and financial risk of more secure employment across the entire portfolio of equipment grants and facility charges.

What are the benefits to researchers and Research Organisations?

A strategic approach to infrastructure, with effective staff development and depth of expertise results in several benefits:

Agile, responsive deployment of resources to meet challenges, changes in strategy or to take advantage of emerging opportunities.

Improved cost recovery. Equipment is appropriately costed on applications.

Staff members are better trained through retention, providing a higher quality service to researchers and improving the delivery and quality of research projects.

Facilities could also provide high-level training to doctoral students on a secondment type basis, enhancing doctoral outcomes and employability in technical and specialist careers in academia and industry.

Facilities can be monitored through KPIs, enabling a better evidenced case of their benefits for maintaining and increasing investment.

Efficiency is improved through reduced waste, duplication and the reduction in internal bureaucracy.

Research users have a comprehensive overview of the available equipment.

The institution has the critical mass of expertise reducing staff turnover. In turn, the provision of an excellent infrastructure portfolio can attract research talent to the organisation in order to be in proximity to high-quality technical and specialist support.

Generation of revenue from business users

Both institutions provide industrial users access to their infrastructure portfolio. This reduces transactional friction and enables industry users to work with both the facilities and academics thus increasing the chances for commercialisation and research impact.

Case study

High performing teams
Formula 1 pit crew

Event speakers likened their specialist function to a Formula 1 pit crew, an example the audience enjoyed and one we are providing here.

Formula 1 is amongst the most prominent motor sports. F1 teams are an investment running into hundreds of millions of pounds, with cars precision engineered to minute tolerances, drivers trained relentlessly and race strategies fine-tuned through data and careful analysis. Underpinning these elements is the F1 pit crew, able to raise and stabilise the F1 car and change all four wheels in 2.5 seconds.

Each member of the pit stop has a clearly defined role. Each wheel has 3 team members assigned to it, removing the tyre, positioning a new one and ratcheting it into place. Movements are carefully choreographed to maximise efficiency and minimise errors, ensuring cars spend the least time possible out of the race. Milliseconds make or break races and pit crews are the unsung heroes of an F1 team.

Crew members hold other roles in the team, they're drawn from the pool of engineers and mechanics, but selected for their ability to work as part of a high-performance machine that ensures each corner of the car is worked at the same speed, preventing unbalancing.

F1 is a highly regulated environment and errors, such as unsafe release, can incur time penalties and fines. The operation is overseen by a crew chief responsible for team safety and the final go/no go decision. Bringing this all together requires a lot of practice and a lot of expertise, but most of all, a high level of trust between team members that everyone will perform their role to their utmost and keep their teammates safe.

The pit crew is much greater than the sum of its parts and McLaren's has set the world record pit stop time at 1.8 seconds. A time humanly impossible to achieve with contributors working alone or at cross purposes.

Our attendees appreciated the analogy to technical and specialist roles in R&I, noting the commonality to team research approaches where the contributions of every team member were essential to something bigger than the sum of its parts and to making the biggest difference possible with each research project.

Appendix 1: event agenda

Driving Research Excellence through institutional support for technical and specialist capability

A UKRI event in partnership with the UK Institute for Technical Skills & Strategy

12 June 2025 | Nottingham Contemporary

- 09:30 – 10:00 Arrival, registration, coffee & networking
- 10:00 – 10:15 Welcome & Opening Remarks: UKRI and ITSS
- 10:15 – 10:45 Opening Keynote: Anne-Marie Coriat, University of Edinburgh
Institutional approaches to professional services modernisation and embedding a high-performance research and innovation culture
- 10:45 – 11:10 UCL – Advanced Research Computing Centre: Donna Swann and Jonathan Cooper
- 11:10 – 11:25 Research Software Engineering at Exeter: Katie Finch

Coffee and networking break

- 11:45 – 12:10 Morning Panel discussion and Q&A: Donna Swann, Jonathan Cooper and Katie Finch
- 12:10 – 12:30 Roundtable Discussion 1: How can shared infrastructure and digital capabilities enable an inclusive and high performing research culture?
- 12:30 – 12:40 Plenary Feedback 1: Each table shares key insights and reflections

Lunch

- 13:30 – 13:45 Research Facility Infrastructure at Bath: Anneke Lubben
- 13:45 – 14:00 Research Technology Platforms at Warwick: Ian Hancox
- 14:00 – 14:25 Afternoon panel discussion and Q&A: Kelly Vere, Ian Hancox and Anneke Lubben

- 14:25 – 14:45 Roundtable Discussion 2: What does good research, technical and specialist leadership look like with increasingly complex and challenging research questions, requiring deeper subject matter, technical and specialist knowledge and skills?
- 14:45 – 14:55 Plenary Feedback 2: Each table shares key insights and reflections

Coffee and networking break

- 15:10 – 15:30 The Hidden REF: Simon Hettrick
- 15:30 – 15:50 UKRI people and teams plan: Nik Ogryzko
- 15:50 – 16:10 Roundtable Discussion 3: How do we encourage the sector to consider the impact of structures and capabilities on research performance and improving research outcomes?
- 16:10 – 16:20 Plenary Feedback 3: Each table shares key insights and reflections
- 16:20 – 16:30 Closing Remarks

Contact talent@ukri.org if you have any questions about this report.

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